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On The Relative Expansion Of Asymmetrical Space-Time

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Abstract: Where is the Centre of the Universe? Do our observations of space-time expansion in the global rest frame prove it to be absolute? However, the laws of SR and "Asymmetry" in time give rise to greater probabilities for the past arrow of time, which violates nature's pre-defined law. Our finite observable part of the universe is not at the center of an infinite plane, and its comoving expansion behaves strangely in relation to the CMB itself. In order to discuss the evolution of space, with the assumption that our current random stage of observations has its origin in chance, another approach to time scales has been introduced in this paper. This approach is based on the time intervals of observed events relative to the frame of reference.

Keywords – Singularity, Big Bang, Spacetime, Relativity, Asymmetry

I. INTRODUCTION

Friedman's equations [1] Observations of red shift in distant galaxies by Georges Lemaître and Edwin Hubble [1] [2] The discovery of Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Radiation [3], as well as current data collection of our universe predicting that the average density of energy and matter in the universe is less than the critical density and that our universe is expanding in nature, have been the foundations of the big bang theory. The Friedman-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) Metric [4], which describes the geometry of our universe based on the assumptions of homogeneity and isotropy, tells us that there is no spatial center and that the universe appears the same in all directions. The image of our universe has been depicted on the global rest frame of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Radiation and spacetime expansion have been described according to the time-varying scale factor $a(t)$.

Einstein's considerations of the initial reference frame in the theory of Special Relativity is a very special case. According to relativity theory, time, length, and space coordinates are not absolute quantities and vary in different frames of reference [5]. Even the speed of light is variable in complete spacetime transformation [6]. The cosmic distances and universe scale factor seem to be relative to cosmic times. To describe the "geometry" of space-time in General Relativity, we may wish to represent a vector in more than one coordinate, which requires the general relativity transformation laws [7]. The big bang itself is a very complex concept; the "asymmetry" in time takes the place in the past arrow of time, which violates the second law of thermodynamics, and past hypothesis introduced in studies to preserve the law [8]. On the other hand, Laws of "Special Relativity" give rise to higher probabilities in past intervals relative to reference frames. If the comoving expansion of the universe is greater than the speed of light c , the peculiar motion of our observable part is considered as a non-zero with respect to the CMB to explain the motion of our universe. In this paper, I attempted to provide a different representation of time intervals based on event time scales rather than the observer's frame of reference in order to explain how our observable finite part evolves on this infinite plane of universe under hypothetical conditions. I attempted to describe the evolution of our universe in the current time by taking into consideration the "present random stage of observations that happened by chance" and the expansion of space with the relative approach based on the observed event's future time intervals for local reference frames.

II. THE BIG BANG AND THE EXPANDING UNIVERSE:

To secure his idea of a spherical, finite, static, and non-expanding universe, Einstein introduced the cosmological constant in 1917 in his best-known field equation of general relativity [9]. Alexander Friedman published two Friedman equations in 1922 to describe the evolution of the universe over time in accordance with general relativity [10].

The 1st Friedman Equation, which describes the rate of universe expansion.

$$\frac{\dot{a}^2 + Kc^2}{a^2} = \frac{8\pi G\rho + \Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (1)$$

And the 2nd Friedman Equation, which describes the rate of universe acceleration.

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3p}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- \dot{a} is universe expansion rate
- \ddot{a} is universe expansion acceleration rate
- K is curvature Parameter
- c is speed of light
- G is Newton's Gravitational constant
- Λ is Cosmological Constant
- ρ is mass density
- P is pressure

The curvature parameter K indicates the shape of the universe as well as the rate of expansion and whether that rate is increasing or decreasing.

If, $K = 0$, the universe will continue to expand at a decreasing rate indefinitely.

If, $K = +1$, The gravitational attraction will eventually stop the universe's expansion.

And if, $K = -1$, the universe will continue to expand indefinitely.

According to Friedman's assumption, the universe has a time-varying scale factor that describes the universe's comoving expansion over time $a(t)$.

Georges Lemaître published a paper in 1927 proposing the idea that the mass of the universe is constant and related to Einstein's cosmological constant, and that the radius of the universe increases without limit from an asymptotic value [1].

$$R_0 \text{ for } t = -\infty \quad (3)$$

Edwin Hubble studied the redshift of distant galaxies in 1929 and proposed a linear relationship between galaxies based on the universe scale factor. The Hubble parameter characterizes the relative growth of distances in unit time [2].

$$H(t) = \frac{\dot{a}(t)}{a(t)} \quad (4)$$

These studies were the impetus for the development of the Big Bang theory.

The prediction of the existence of cosmic microwave background (CMB) radiation by Ralph Alpher in 1951 [3], as well as a 1998 study that discovered the universe is accelerating and the cosmological constant is positive " $\Lambda > 0$ " [11], offered additional evidence for the big bang theory. These studies provided a clear picture of the expansion and evolution of our universe over time.

According to big bang theory universe started from the singularity and singularity expanded as the universe today we know. The cosmic inflation epoch of the big bang theory is the reason for the greater expansion of space time at initial stage and to cool down universe. Post inflation period regular expansion of space time appeared. The balloon analogy is most used metaphor to give the picture & explain the evolution of universe to general public by worldwide astrophysicists [12]. In balloon metaphor spherical expanding model of universe is used. To imagine the picture of expansion of the universe, we have to picture universe as a balloon. If we draw bunch of dots on the balloon and blow it up, all the points on balloon will expand. We are not adding extra balloon material here, just fabric of balloon being stretch causing points on balloon separate. This is exactly how universe works according general relativity.

When the scientific community explains the big bang and singularity, a common misconception arises: where is the position of the singularity? or, more broadly, where is the center of the universe? The Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) Metric [4], which derives from universe models, is based on the assumption that the universe is homogeneous and isotropic, which means it has no spatial center and appears the same in all directions. The singularity has evolved into the universe we know today. According to scale factor $a(t)$, expansion increases as time increases, and the center of singularity expansion is located in time, allowing us to find the center of the universe in the past arrow of time. And, conveniently, we can point in any direction for the past time, and it will coincide with the centre.

According to theory, the center of space-time expansion began at $t = 0$, followed by the cosmic inflation epoch at a rate greater than c (Universal physical constant), and space-time expanded indefinitely. However, at the Planck epoch of the Big Bang $T_p = 10^{-43}$ seconds, the fundamentals of General Relativity decompose, and we cannot effectively describe the position of two points or the time variation between two events without a theory of quantum gravity. This is commonly known as quantum foam [13]. It makes describing what the universe was like at $t = 0$ difficult. If we can trace the expansion of the universe back to before the Planck era, it is possible that the universe began with infinite energy density, with all points of space and time overlapping each other. This is referred to as a cosmological singularity at times. This type of singularity is more of an asymptote in our ability to describe events in time and points in space than a physical state at $t = 0$.

The picture of our universe has been depicted using the global cosmic rest frame as the reference frame for the CMB. A cosmic rest frame is a velocity with no discernible Doppler shift in any direction. However, we don't see a perfectly distributed temperature distribution when we observe the CMB from our moving platform, planet Earth. Because of the earth's and solar system's motion, the CMB is Doppler-shifted, creating the appearance of bands of blue and red-shifted CMB radiation. Even in the cosmic rest frame, current observations of the local universe are finding the peculiar motion of clusters is not 0 and that the bulk flow of the local universe is occurring [14], We will go over this in more detail in subsequent topics.

If these are the cases, the universe does not have a defined $t = 0$, but rather evolves from a point infinitely close to $t = 0$, or as close as can be physically described, which may very well be the aforementioned Planck time. In this scenario, we cannot

approach the singularity of the big bang behind the Planck era and cannot locate the center of spacetime expansion. Even though cosmic time is also "relative" to reference frames, the big bang singularity cannot be considered an absolute quantity. But the question is, can we define the center of space-time expansion in local frames? We should narrate the expansion from present to future without approaching the singularity in past time because "asymmetry" in time does not give us an actual image of the past [15].

III. ASYMMETRY OR RATHER TIME RELATIVITY:

According to Special Relativity, length and time are not absolute quantities. But since the length is relative, space cannot be absolute. The Lorentz factor expresses how much the measurement of time, length, and some other physical quantities change for an object while it is moving. The expression appears in several equations in special relativity.

The Lorentz factor γ is defined as [5]

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{V^2}{c^2}}} = \frac{dt}{d\tau} \tag{6}$$

where:

V is the relative velocity between inertial reference frames,

c is the speed of light in a vacuum,

t is coordinate time,

τ is the proper time for an observer.

The proper time $\Delta\tau$ Between two events is the time interval as observed in a coordinate system where two events take place at the same position. This is not always possible. The proper time is the time interval measured by the observer who doesn't move relative to this position. It is time measured by a clock that is stationary concerning the observer.

In General Relativity to describe the "geometry" of space-time, we may wish to represent a vector in more than one coordinate system and to convert back and forth between two representations [7].

In the nonlinear Transformation of contravariant vectors, we have

$$v'^{\mu} = v^{\kappa} \frac{\partial x'^{\mu}}{\partial x^{\kappa}} \tag{7}$$

$$v'_{\mu} = v_{\kappa} \frac{\partial x^{\kappa}}{\partial x'^{\mu}} \tag{8}$$

The metric is a rank-2 tensor, and transforms analogously:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\kappa\lambda} \frac{\partial x^{\kappa}}{\partial x'^{\mu}} \frac{\partial x^{\lambda}}{\partial x'^{\nu}} \tag{9}$$

In terms of cosmological distance measurement [16], The "Light travel distance" is the distance travelled by a photon. The "proper distance" is the separation between two distant objects at a given time, and the "comoving distance" is the separation between two distant objects at any given time in the past or future. The cosmic scale factor is the ratio of their correct distance at time t ($D(t)$) to their current proper distance (D^0).

$$a(t) = D(t)/D^0 \tag{10}$$

The relative speed of light is variable under the complete Space time transformation, and Einstein's constant speed of light in an isolated frame of reference is a necessary condition for the relative variable speed of light. Because there is no natural inertial reference frame, the condition of an inertial reference frame is very unique [6]. Because special relativity only applies to inertial reference frames, it is impossible to detect inertial frame motion while within the frame, so we cannot detect absolute motion or rest [17].

In accordance with the Copernican principle, "we are typical observers of events" [18]. In these instances, if time is relative to reference frames and the geometry of space-time is relative to coordinate systems, we need transformation laws to calculate the rate of expansion in non-inertial frames. The proper distance and scale factor will also become relative to the frame of reference, implying that space-time expansion is a relative phenomenon, and the big bang singularity expansion time $t = 0$ will appear at different intervals for different cosmic times.

The second law of thermodynamics states that disorder in an equilibrium system increases over time. To preserve the integrity of the second law, time should be "symmetric" in both past and future directions where the entropy of the system decreases at the same rate in past time. The big bang is an extremely unlikely event, and "asymmetry" in time occurs to describe the evolution of past time intervals of the universe, which violates the second law of thermodynamics. To regain the glory of pre-defined nature's law, the "past hypothesis" was introduced based on the "inflationary" model to describe the specialness in the initial stage of the

big bang where the universe started in a low-entropy state [8]. In his work "Conformal Cyclic Cosmology," Penrose counters the inflationary model with a model based on the "Weyl curvature hypothesis" (WCH) [19]. According to Roger, When the second law is a crucial component, *there is always a far more probable set of initial conditions that would lead to this same state of affairs, namely one is which the second law was violated prior to the situation now!*

As aforementioned, if time and distances in the universe are not absolute quantities in local reference frames, higher probabilities occur in the past arrow of time where contraction of space must be considered based on current scenarios, resulting in a lack of specialness at the beginning of the universe. As a result, deriving the hypothesis to introduce the specialness for $t = 0$ of singularity is unethical. To date, not much work has been carried out to discuss the "Asymmetry" in time in the context of Special Relativity. However, because the "arrow of time" is one-directional, and photons are still the most commonly used tool for human observations of nature [20], light takes time to reach the observer from the event it originated according to the reference frames and geometry of spacetime. From the Anthropic view, our present random stage of observations simply came by chance and we need to focus on the evolution of space-time from present to future intervals as a one-directional "arrow of time".

The following representations of time at the event have been considered for a relativistic flow of Spacetime with consideration our current state of observations came by chance and the flow of time is one-directional. (It should be noted that representations are based not only on the observer's frame of reference, but also on the event itself.)

T_0 for the present time of the event.

$\Delta T \downarrow$ for the past interval of the event observed at the present time of reference frame.

$\Delta T \uparrow$ for the future interval of the event

Whereas the present time of event T_0 is relative to reference frames, and consideration of expansion of space-time will appear in future intervals of event $\Delta T \uparrow$. the past intervals of event $\Delta T \downarrow$ which are observed at the present time of reference frame of the observer, should be considered as the contraction of the universe in the frame of the event itself, but at the observer's end expansion of the universe will consider as it appears at the present time of reference frame and flow of time for the reference frame will be from present to future as considered the present stage of observation has originated by chance.

IV. OBSERVATIONS OF OUR UNIVERSE IN TIME INTERVALS OF EVENTS:

The radius of the observable part of the universe, which is 46.4 billion light-years [21], is the finite part of the universe's infinite plane. Kashlinsky's debatable observations of galaxy clusters [14] in 2008 revealed that distant galaxies are pushed apart from each other without a preferred direction as space between them grows, a phenomenon is known as the Hubble flow, which is equal in all directions. Furthermore, the peculiar motion of galaxies should not have a preferred direction. The added peculiar motion of all clusters should cancel out in the CMB frame, but observations on the largest scale seemed to reveal that galaxies' motions do not cancel out. The contentious evidence of slight drift of galaxies in one preferred direction, establishing the explanation for such "Dark Flow," would fit naturally within a specific inflationary model. And these observations revealed that galaxies are moving in one direction outside of the observable part of our universe, which could be due to higher gravitational pull. If the universe model is infinite and light can only reach us from a finite distance as the comoving distance between gravitationally non-bound galaxies increases, then the entire observable part of the universe must also comove relative to the CMB.

As shown in Figure 1, the expansion of the universe began according to the inflationary model at $t = 0$ in reference to the CMB. Because photons (CMB) do not experience time and, according to physical laws, photons can reach any interval of time, CMB can counter future intervals of events without experiencing time. As we defined event time intervals in the topic " **Asymmetry or rather Time Relativity**," we will consider our observable part of the universe as an event in reference to the CMB. At T_0 of the event observations of our universe were carried out, and at the future interval $\Delta T \uparrow$, the universe has expanded as it is today, In reference to CMB itself. If the CMB is distributed uniformly throughout space and the universe's comoving expansion has a speed greater than c (CMB), the entire observable part of our universe will have non-zero peculiar motion and will move in either direction in space because the diameter of 92.8 billion light years is finite and not at the center of an infinite plane. As previously stated, this event will move faster than the speed of light; in this case, any other reference frames will disagree on the order of events in time scale, and we cannot predict the future and past orders of the universe relative to any other reference frame because events occur in a space-like separation (Refer Figure 1).

Light takes time to reach us from the edges of the observable universe in our observations of the local universe. As shown in Figure 2, observing the event (Galaxy or cluster) at "Point P" at the edge of the observable part of our universe in our reference frame "S" means we are observing the past interval of "event P" $\Delta T \downarrow$ at the present proper time τ of reference frame "S". As previously demonstrated, the expansion of space time began at T_0 with the "event P." Until the time photons from the event reach us, the point P will have moved away from the observable part to us (Figure 3) in its own future intervals $\Delta T \uparrow$ as space expands, and we will observe the past intervals of event $\Delta T \downarrow$. In other non-inertial reference frames, the "event P" past intervals $\Delta T \downarrow$ will be relative to their own proper time. As previously stated, the past intervals of an event should not be regarded as a contraction of space time in the reference frames of observers because they occurred at the present proper time of reference frames, but for the event itself, space expansion occurs in the future intervals $\Delta T \uparrow$.

In these cases, observations of spacetime expansion are carried out in the observers' reference frames at their own proper time $\Delta\tau$ based on the past intervals of event $\Delta T \downarrow$, but the real-time expansion of space begins at the time of observation of events T_0 and space expands from the place of the event in a time of future intervals $\Delta T \uparrow$ in local references of cosmology, where the past arrow of time is non-significant as this model describes the evolution of the universe and the expansion of space on the time intervals of events and not only on the time scales of reference frames, taking into account that the current stage of observations happened by chance. These scenarios lead to the conclusion that the future evolution of the universe and expansion of space is based

not only on the time scale of reference frames but also on the time intervals of observed events at the present time of relative references with one directional arrow of time.

V. CONCLUSION:

We discussed studies that describe the evolution of our universe over time in this paper. Friedman's equations which are based on General relativity describe the shape of the universe and the rate of expansion according to the curvature parameter " k ". The time-varying scale factor $a(t)$, which describes the universe's comoving expansion, and Lemaître's assumptions in his studies present the expanding universe model. Later, Hubble observed redshift in distant galaxies, and the Big Bang theory was born, in which our expanding universe began from a singularity. The discovery of the CMB and observations of the universe provided the necessary evidence for the Big Bang theory and the expanding model of our universe. The early high energy photons, CMB radiation, which is distributed throughout space, provide much important data to describe the picture of our universe. When the scientific community explains the big bang, a common misconception arises in the general public's mind: where is the center of the universe?

We discussed the FLRW metric, which derives universe models and the concepts of homogeneity and isotropy. According to theory, there is no spatial center of our universe since singularity has grown over time to become the universe, we know today based on the scale factor $a(t)$, with the center of the universe being located in past time at $t = 0$. However, we cannot approach the $t=0$, cause behind the Planck era of the big bang, $T_p = 10^{-43}$ seconds, the fundamentals of general relativity do not work and we require the theory of quantum gravity, making it challenging to describe the universe at $t = 0$. The picture of our universe has been depicted in the terms of the global rest frame, which is the rest frame of the CMB, but recent studies have revealed that even in the frame of reference of the CMB, the peculiar motion of galaxies is non-zero. In these scenarios, we can't get close to the big-bang singularity behind the Planck era and can't find the center of space-time expansion at $t = 0$.

According to SR and GR, time, length, and distance are relative to reference frames rather than absolute quantities. The Lorentz factor expresses changes in length, time, and other physical quantities in different moving frames, and General Relativity transformation laws describe the "*geometry*" of space-time in multiple coordinate systems. Because special relativity only applies to inertial reference frames, the condition of an inertial reference frame is very special because there is no such thing in nature. Even the relative speed of light is variable under the entire Space-time transformation. The past hypothesis was introduced in studies to derive the specialness at the initial stage of the inflationary model to preserve the second law of thermodynamics. However, Penrose's work contradicts to the specialness of initial stage, and laws of special relativity give rise to higher probabilities in time flip conditions in non-inertial reference frames. If time and distances are relative to reference frames, the time-varying scale factor $a(t)$ becomes relative to the observers, and space-time expansion and, eventually, the big bang singularity becomes relative to different cosmic times, the factor will violate the representation of second law as "*asymmetry*" in time occurs. To describe the relativistic flow of Spacetime with one directional arrow of time, I depicted another representation of time scales based on time intervals of an event for relative local reference frames, where T_0 represents the present time of the event, $\Delta T \downarrow$ represents the past interval of event, and $\Delta T \uparrow$ represents the future intervals of event.

If the model of the universe is infinite, and light can only reach us from a finite distance as the comoving distance between gravitationally non-bound galaxies increases, and the CMB is distributed uniformly throughout space, and the comoving expansion of the universe has a speed greater than c (CMB), the observable part of our universe will have non-zero peculiar motion and will shift in space-like intervals. In this case, any other reference frame will disagree on the order of events on a time scale, and we cannot predict the future and past orders of the universe relative to any other reference frame because events take place in a space-like separation. In the final section, I express the Relative Expansion of Spacetime in local reference frames, where the expansion of space begins at the observed event's present time T_0 , and space expands from the location of the event in a time of future intervals of event $\Delta T \uparrow$ that are relative to the frame of reference. Because light takes time to reach the observer from a distance, the observation of space expansion is carried out in the past interval of event $\Delta T \downarrow$ in the proper time $\Delta\tau$ of reference frame.

To summarise this work, I represent another time scale that is based on the time intervals of events rather than the time intervals of reference frames, and the future evolution of the universe is based on the time intervals of observed events at present of relative references with one directional arrow of time with the consideration of our current observation random stage came by chance.

FIGURES:

Figure 1: Space time expansion and comoving finite observable part in the frame of CMB.

Figure 2: Event observation at the current time of the local reference frame.

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Figure 3: Position of event in its future intervals at the present time of reference frame

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